

To Take Law Seriously. Via quantum physics, mechanics.
We Vote for Mindful Lawyers/Judges, becoming Political Actors.
For Development, Unity of Diversity, Inclusion, Sustainability.

Abstract

This year we celebrate Lautsi case, pronounced 10 years ago. Today we go forward. We are living in the changing times. All and everything are developing, thought, conscience, awareness, including. We proceed from a deep unifying effect between the peoples from various countries, the Crucifix case has produced. The Lautsi case bears witness that people unity needs high values and the Christianity remains at the heart. We call for sharing the goal of demystifying the discipline of law. We share the opinion that freedom of thought, conscience and religion should be understood in terms of individual human rights, not minority rights and we are sure, this freedom should include as spirituality so mindfulness. A vision that leads us to explore, in an amazing perspective, fundamental questions still unresolved, from the setting up of law to that of politicians/judges/lawyers themselves. This paper shows how creative models based on the laws and precedents can fully implement the law of cause and effect in manner of quantum theory.

Keywords

Lautsi case, change, justice, freedom of thought, conscience and religion, ECtHR; spirituality, mindfulness, politics, judiciary, lawyering, quantum physics, mechanics.

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Development and change. This year we celebrate Lautsi case¹, pronounced 10 years ago. We proceed from a deep unifying effect between the peoples from various countries, the Crucifix case has produced. The Lautsi case bears witness that people unity needs high values and the Christianity remains at the heart.
Today we go forward. We call for sharing the goal of demystifying the discipline of law.

¹ On March 18, 2011, the European Court of Human Rights, sitting as a Grand Chamber (“GC”), pronounced its judgment in the case of *Soile Lautsi and Others v. Italy*. (*Lautsi v. Italy*, App. No. 30814/06, 2011 Eur. Ct. H.R. (G.C.)) By this final judgment, which overturned a unanimous judgment rendered on November 3, 2009, by the Second Section of the Strasbourg Court (A Section is an administrative entity, and a Chamber is a judicial formation of the Court within a given Section. The Court has five Sections in which Chambers are formed. Each Section has a President, a Vice-President, and a number of other judges), the Grand Chamber (The Grand Chamber is made up of 17 judges: the Court’s President and Vice-Presidents, the Section Presidents, and the national judge, together with other judges selected by drawing of lots. The initiation of proceedings before the Grand Chamber takes two different forms: referral and relinquishment. After a Chamber judgment has been delivered, the parties may request referral of the case to the Grand Chamber and such requests are accepted on an exceptional basis. A panel of judges of the Grand Chamber decides whether or not the case should be referred to the Grand Chamber for fresh consideration. Cases are also sent to the Grand Chamber when relinquished by a Chamber, although this is also exceptional. The Chamber to which a case is assigned can relinquish it to the Grand Chamber if the case raises a serious question affecting the interpretation of the Convention or if there is a risk of inconsistency with a previous judgment of the Court. See *The Court, EUROPEAN COURT OF HUMAN RIGHTS*, (Aug. 4, 2012, 3:18 PM), <http://www.echr.coe.int/ECHR/EN/Header/The+Court/The+Court/The+Grand+Chamber/>) decided, by fifteen votes to two, that the compulsory display of crucifixes in Italian State-school classrooms did not violate Article 2 of the first Protocol of the European Convention on Human Rights. (*Lautsi*, 2011 Eur. Ct. H.R. §§ 77–78)

We share the opinion that freedom of thought, conscience and religion should be understood in terms of individual human rights, not minority rights² and we are sure, this freedom should include as spirituality so mindfulness.

We are living in the changing times. All and everything are developing, thought, conscience, awareness, including.

Now in the world there is a kind of believing without belonging³ Europeans remain religious, in the sense more close to the spirituality, their approach is eclectic, and they borrow ideas from several traditions.⁴ Their approach is not associated with a given culture. This phenomenon is sometimes described as private spirituality.⁵ There has been a great increase in the past 20-25 years in those who describe themselves as *spiritual but not religious*. (SBNRs)⁶ Christopher Partridge⁷ calls this trend one of the most significant developments in Western religion over the past 50 years, noting that: "There is in the West . . . a move away from traditional forms of belief, which have developed within religious institutions, towards forms of belief that focus on the self, on nature or simply on "life" . . . There is a move away from a "religion" that focuses on things that are considered to be external to the self (God, the Bible, the church) to "spirituality"—that which focuses on "the self" and is personal and interior."⁸

A lot of modern people pick and choose religious beliefs, doctrines, ideas, thoughts and practices and they are mixing and matching them, as they would select food in a cafeteria. Sociologists talk about this trend as a *cafeteria religion*,⁹ or as *church-free spirituality*.¹⁰ Legal scholar Rebecca French calls this *grocery cart religion* and summarizes it well: a grocery cart religious practice has only the rituals and ethical boundaries that the practitioner explicitly agrees to take on. Instead of following a revealed canon, the individual fits the interesting parts of different religions together into a structured personal spiritual practice.¹¹

We are in the period of transformation. All and everything, including politics, law, law practices and practices in law, should be transformed.

For the purpose of **development** and **change**, we apply the Critical Thinking.¹²

Critical thinking is a rich concept that has been developing throughout the past 2,500 years. The term *critical thinking* has its roots in the mid-late 20th century. There are

2 Roy Olivier, Religious Freedom and Diversity in a Comparative European Perspective// <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/79665887.pdf>

3 *Introduction* in Christopher Partridge, ed, Encyclopedia of New Religions 17, Lion Publishing (2004).

4 <https://europeanvaluesstudy.eu/?s=religion>

5 <https://www.apologeticsindex.org/7514-cafeteria-religion>

6 Mercadante Linda A, Belief Without Borders: Inside the Minds of the Spiritual but not Religious, Oxford University Press (2014).

7 Christopher Hugh Partridge (1961) is an author, editor, professor at Lancaster University, and founding Co-director of the Centre for the Study of Religion and Popular Culture. According to Gordon Lynch, Partridge is a leading scholar of topics in popular culture.

8 *Introduction* in Christopher Partridge, ed, Encyclopedia of New Religions 17, Lion Publishing (2004).

9 On the Cafeteria Christianity see: Boot Alexander, Religion Without Faith, Christianity Without Christ, God and Man According to Tolstoy, Palgrave Macmillan US, 41–47 (2009); Dunne Tad, Faith, Charity, Hope, Lonergan Workshop. 5, 49–70 (1985); Various UC Berkeley Seismic Guidelines, Appendix II: Ground Motion Time Histories for the UC Berkeley Campus. (2003-06-03); Aronoff Craig E, Ward, John L, The Role of Values in Uniting Family and Business, Family Business Values, Palgrave Macmillan US, 21–26 (2011)

10 See: Dalferth Ingolf U. I Determine What God Is!: Theology in the Age of "Cafeteria Religion" (April 1, 2000) <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/004057360005700102>

11 See generally: French Rebecca, Shopping for Religion: The Change in Everyday Religious Practice and Its Importance to the Law, 51 Buffalo Law Review, 127, 165, 166 (2003)

12 More details: <https://www.criticalthinking.org/pages/defining-critical-thinking/766>

different definitions which together form a substantive and trans-disciplinary conception of *critical thinking*. A statement by Michael Scriven & Richard Paul, presented at the 8th Annual International Conference on Critical Thinking and Education Reform, Summer 1987: "Critical thinking is the intellectually disciplined process of actively and skillfully conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information gathered from, or generated by, observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication, as a guide to belief and action. In its exemplary form, it is based on universal intellectual values that transcend subject matter divisions: clarity, accuracy, precision, consistency, relevance, sound evidence, good reasons, depth, breadth, and fairness. "

We start from the points:

changing human being is changing the reality;

changing human being is changing the thought, conscience, awareness, consciousness (religion);

the changing conscience is changing the freedom of thought, conscience (religion).

We follow the affirmation attributed to Albert Einstein: "The problems that exist in the world today cannot be solved by the level of thinking that created them"¹³.

Seeking *the new level of thinking*, we propose *the mindfulness*.

Why mindfulness¹⁴? While one can be a spiritual person and a mindful person, one can be mindful, observing their surroundings in the present moment, without being spiritual. Mindfulness could be applied globally.

Let's pay our attention to "*The maxim of the Five W's (and one H)*", that for a subject to be considered complete it must answer a checklist of six questions, each of which reflects a part of world. It is a formula for getting the "global" story on the subject.

I KEEP six honest serving-men

(They taught me all I knew);

Their names are What and Why and When

And How and Where and Who.

I send them over land and sea,

I send them east and west...

(R.Kipling)

Mindfulness could have a unifying effect between various judges, lawyers and professionals. Mindful Lawyering is the key to creative problem solving.

How mindfulness influences jurisprudence and politics. It seems more appropriate to assume that judicial decisions/legal resolutions are shaped and channeled by the obligation of courts and lawyers to deliver principled decisions, to make choices resting on legal basis. We claim that the application of law is always creative. That is why we are (also) interested in the question of how mindfulness of lawyers influences jurisprudence and politics.

¹³ https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/albert_einstein_121993; In The New Quotable Einstein, Alice Calaprice suggests that this phrase attributed to Einstein could be a paraphrase of two quotes from a 1946 article.

¹⁴ We started with Jon Kabat-Zinn's "classic" description of mindfulness.

<https://www.theguardian.com/lifeandstyle/2017/oct/22/mindfulness-jon-kabat-zinn-depression-trump-grenfell#:~:text=Kabat%2DZinn%20has%20defined%20mindfulness,pain%2C%20both%20physical%20and%20emotional>.

Our core topic is the importance of legal ideas and legal doctrine for legal activity, and the inclusion of mindfulness in law in legal ideas and legal doctrine.

We assume that legal procedures, legal ideology shape not only the interactions but also the preferences of the judges/lawyers and of society at large.

In this perspective, judges/lawyers shape politics through the development of legal doctrine, legal ideas, through the mindfulness in law, too. The process of shaping legal doctrine into another direction unfolds step by step over long periods of time.

We would agree with Volcansek¹⁵ that research on European courts should look more closely at the politics of judicial action. We go forward: we look at the reality created by our acting in mindfulness; we look at the politics of our different legal practices, mindfulness including.

This approach has following advantages:

- A priori, political actors try to influence the development of legal concepts and tools and we evaluate that only mindful politics could influence our mindfulness in law.
- A legal choice or a court decision does not occur out of nowhere, but responds to a legal discourse unfolding over a longer time period – months or years. In most cases/legal issues the universe of competing legal concepts/legal ideas is obvious before a judge makes a decision, a lawyer makes a choice, and he/she merely picks one of them, perhaps with some modifications (e.g. paragraph 56 of the decision demonstrates that the concept of neutrality applied by ECtHR in the Lautsi v Italy case represents a transposition of the French version of strong secularism).

This means that political interests have to be translated into legal language in order to become successful. But readers could have some questions regarding the thoughts, ideas, concepts and translations emerged via the mindfulness, for example: how are they linked to political interests, which intellectual and material resources are used to help them become the dominant norm, to what extent are they selected by a judge/lawyer?

Methodologically, the Design Thinking, Complexity, Science Approach could be applied. For the implementation the meditation could be used.

How politics influences jurisprudence and viceversa. We do not live in a just world. This may be the least controversial claim one could make in political and legal theories. But it is much less clear what discretionary justice/creative lawyering on a world scale might mean.¹⁶ Today the modern concepts and theories of discretionary justice/creative lawyering are in the stages of formation, and it is not clear what the main questions are, let alone the main possible issues. Many scholars explore the role of the EU as a promoter of its own standards and values abroad. We agree that in the field of law European Court of Human Rights acts as a unique laboratory of concepts and tools (M.Ventura¹⁷). We argue that it is true and mistake, both. The world outside EU/ECtHR should influence EU/ECtHR and, of course, *vice versa*, the EU/ECtHR should influence

15 Volcansek Mary L, Comparative Judicial Politics (2019)

16 See in detail: Vinson Kathleen Elliott, Moppett Samantha Alexis, George Shailini Jandial, Mindful Lawyering: The Key to Creative Problem Solving, (2018)

17 M. Ventura underlined that « [...] the development of a European jurisdiction is highly valuable thanks to four basic virtues and, in particular, to its role: 1) as a counter balance to denominational majorities and to religious nationalism; 2) as a unique laboratory of concepts and tools; 3) as a contribution to national debate and evolution; 4) and as an instrument for forging a supranational open space of religious diversity, freedom of thought and social cohesion», Law and Religion Issues in Strasbourg and Luxembourg: The Virtues of European Courts, (November 2011), available at <http://www.eui.eu/Projects/ReligioWest/Documents/events/conferencePapers/Ventura.pdf>.

other world. The same way, the legal world should influence another part of the world and *vice versa*. For example, we see a lot of problems in the area of judiciary in many countries. The procedural legislations were renewed, the justice improvement is going on. But there is not only this one way of justice improvement. There is another important way. There is another part of the world that influences justice.

That is why we are (also) interested in the question of how politics influences jurisprudence and *vice versa*.

We consider that courts and legal firms are influential political actors and call to share the goal of demystifying the discipline of law. We take law seriously.

Once one takes law seriously, the question arises of whether we can conceptualize judicial/legal behavior as a choice between political or judicial/legal action.

In our monograph on *Judicial Discretion (2005)*, we emphasized that in trial legal clarity and accuracy can never be achieved, but judicial discretion always involves political decisions.

To proceed let's bring to your attention's two quotes:

"Climate change is happening, humans are causing it, and I think this is perhaps the most serious environmental issue facing us,"¹⁸ - Bill Nye¹⁹ notes.

The second phrase is attributed to Charles de Gaulle: "Politics is too serious a matter to be left to the politicians."²⁰

As the quality of the tree is recognized from the fruits, so the true nature of politics is recognized by what it does, not by what it proclaims.

The obvious failure of ordinary political/judicial/legal thinking/interpretation to create a world of peace and justice should suggest to us that we look further, deeper, for guides to action.

We all know, politics sucks. It is largely a playground for (individual and national) egos that are fixated on power and self-advantage.

We envision politics as a humanitarian enterprise focused on the betterment and upliftment of all human societies. We vote for mindful judges, lawyers, become influential political actors.

We seek to shed light on how to humanize legal firms/judiciary/politics and--dare we hope-- lawyers, judges and politicians. Delightfully, even mafia makes sense.

How can the wisdom not guide us in that most human of activities called 'conflict resolution'?

The politics qualifies starting from its "heart". In mindfulness language, the "heart" is the center, the nucleus, which moves and gives "color" and depth to thoughts, words and actions. The heart of any politics is a politician, a lawmaker (a legislator)²¹, a lawyer, a judge²². They all apply law and discretion/creativity. We basically disagree with the argument that discretion/creativity should play a role only rarely, but that, in most cases,

18 https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/bill_nye_437504

19 Bill Nye is an engineer-turned-science-educator and is currently a popular media figure, well known for promoting science in various mass media formats.

20 <https://www.forbes.com/quotes/1542/>

21 Legislator is a synonym of lawmaker. Lawmaker is a synonym of legislator. As nouns the difference between lawmaker and legislator is that lawmaker is one who makes or enacts laws while legislator is someone who creates or enacts law, especially a member of a legislative body.

22 The role of judges as lawmakers has over the years been the subject of much discussion. That this is so, it is so as a result of conscious decision-making by the judges. Judge could be a lawmaker, doing conscious decision-making. See in detail: Bingham Tom, *The Business of Judging. Selected Essays and Speeches* (2000).

the application of law should be “fairly straightforward” (De Franciscis, Maria Elisabetta/Rosella Zannini²³).

We argue that justice/good lawyering/just policies depend on discretion/creativity. Not what enters a politician, a lawmaker, a judge/lawyer does unjust policies, injustice/bad lawyering, but what comes out of politician, lawmaker, judge/lawyer does unjust policies, injustice/bad lawyering.

Using the universal wisdom Jesus says: "What goes into someone's mouth does not defile them, but what comes out of their mouth, that is what defiles them."²⁴ This is the maxim for everyone, the axiom of any life's puzzle, including politics, justice and lawyering. In fact, all wars, damages and injustices come from the heart.

The nucleus of a political actor's, a lawmaker's, a judge's, a lawyer's personality should be like a rock: discretion/creativity that knows unjust policies, injustice/bad lawyering comes from the heart.

Human being heart is therefore comparable to a large container. If a politician, a lawmaker, a judge, a lawyer is able to fill it with truth, with good, with just, his discretion/creativity, his actions, his choices will be ethic and will not do unjust policies, injustice/bad lawyering. It depends on listening, on the welcome a politician, a lawmaker, a judge, a lawyer reserves for **"Discretio est discernere per legem quid sit justum"**.

We intend to offer what has been missing from so much progressive theory and practice: ways of bringing peace right into the heart of lawyer/judge/political actor and heat of the struggle. Dharma and Judiciary/Politics/Lawyering. Mindful Politics, it's a marriage made here, that great, rich melting pot of contradictions.

²³ See in detail: https://www.mpifg.de/pu/mpifg_dp/dp07-5.pdf

²⁴ Matthew, 11-15

Mindful Politics has gathered the big names-- ex UN Secretary-General Dag Hammarskjöld,²⁵ Vl.Solovjev,²⁶ Ivan Ilyin,²⁷ Teilhard de Chardin,²⁸ William A Tiller,²⁹ Carlo Rovelli,³⁰ **Thich Nhat Hanh**,³¹ even **the Dalai Lama** himself--around an ancient idea whose time is more relevant than ever: that the enlightened governance of a society, the enlightened judiciary transcend issues of gender, class, race--even partisanship. We go into Mindful Politics, doing just that, gently pushing the readers to think beyond religion, drawing upon ancient wisdom to cope with the violence and insecurity of our time, giving the readers inspiration and hope. Just imagine mindful politicians, lawyers, judges! Imagine them united by some high value!

25 Dag Hjalmar Agne Carl Hammarskjöld (1905–1961) was a Swedish diplomat, economist, writer and public official. He was president of the Bank of Sweden, but became known internationally as UN Secretary-General. He held the position for two consecutive terms, from 1953 until his death in 1961, which occurred due to a plane crash in southern Africa during a mission of peace. He became a role model in moral leadership to most of his successors and many more people all over the world. Both in his work and in his speeches he promoted an attitude of international service. He was posthumously awarded the Nobel Peace Prize for his humanitarian activity. U.S. President John F. Kennedy called Hammarskjöld *the greatest statesman of our century*. (Linnér, Sture; Åström, Sverker. UN Secretary-General Hammarskjöld: Reflections and Personal Experiences (The 2007 Dag Hammarskjöld Lecture). Uppsala University,28 (2008). This is the translated text of the 2007 Dag Hammarskjöld Lecture given by Sture Linnér and Sverker Åström at Uppsala University on 15 October 2007, http://www.daghammarskjold.se/wp-content/uploads/2007/10/Dh_lecture_2007.pdf

26 Vladimir Sergejevich Solovjev (1853 - 1900) is a Russian philosopher, poet, pamphleteer, literary critic; honorary academician of the Imperial Academy of Sciences in the category of fine literature (1900), played a significant role in the development of Russian philosophy and poetry at the end of the 19th century and in the spiritual renaissance of the early -20th century. He stood at the origins of the Russian "spiritual revival" at the beginning of the 20th century, influenced the religious philosophy of Nikolai Berdyaev, Sergei Bulgakov, Sergei and Yevgeny Trubetskoy, Pavel Florensky, Semyon Frank, as well as the work of the Symbolist poets Andrei Bely, Alexander Blok and others. He founded a movement known as Christian philosophy. The philosophical legacy of Vl. Solovjev is a significant page in Russian social thought in the second half of the 19th century. Vl.Solovjev is one of the central figures in Russian philosophy of the 19th century both in his scientific contribution and in the influence he exerted on the views of scientists. Solovjev objected to the division of Christianity into Catholicism and Orthodoxy and defended the ideas of ecumenism. He developed a new approach to the study of man, which became predominant in Russian philosophy and psychology of the late 19th - early 20th centuries. (Yaroshevsky M.G. Ch. VIII. The development of psychology in Russia. 3. University professors. Vl. S. Solovjev: the neo-Christian concept of the soul // History of psychology from antiquity to the middle of the XX century (Russian), M (1996). Solovjev posed many ideological problems that are relevant to this day. The problem of the relationship between culture and politics is among them. The problem of the relationship between culture and politics was solved by Solovjev both in theoretical terms and in connection with the transformation of the socio-political situation in Russia. Consideration of the legacy of Solovjev from this perspective allows a deeper understanding of the various facets of his proposed solution to the problem of the relationship between culture and politics.

27 Ivan Alexandrovich Ilyin (1883–1954) is Russian philosopher and legal scholar. Although forbidden under the Soviet regime, Ilyin`s thoughts and works have come to be more and more appreciated over the last twenty years, especially since his earthly remains were re-interred in Russia in 2005. It is possible to say that he is the favourite Russian thinker of our times. Like all prophets, however, he was of course mainly ignored, unappreciated and even persecuted in his own times. Today, Ilyin is understood to be the voice of the faithful Russian emigration, a spiritual leader, a teacher, a prophet, a visionary preacher. His prophetic insights have been justified since the fall of Communism and the huge interest in his works there now. Ilyin, who died over half a century ago, is the prophet of the new Russia which is being born and which alone can give the contemporary world a viable future, providing that it is given time to grow to fruition in contemporary Russia. One of the problems he worked on was the question: what has eventually led Russia to the tragedy of the revolution?

28 Pierre Teilhard de Chardin, S.J. (1881 – 1955), was a French Jesuit priest and scientist, professor of geology at the Catholic Institute in Paris, director of the National Geologic Survey of China, and director of the National Research Center of France. He charted a new path in reconciling Christian theology with evolutionary science. Teilhard de Chardin was a prophet, a great intuitive, a mind open to the spirit (*grace*, say the clergymen), an excellent intelligence who knew how to look from above and had a multimedia vision of things which is the evolutionary vision.

29 William A. Tiller is emeritus professor of Science and Engineering of Materials, at Stanford University. Tiller spent 34 years in academia, after having been a consultative physicist at Westinghouse Research Laboratories for nine years, he has published over 250 scientific papers.

It must be remembered that the basis of everything and all in reality is **the causality (physics)³², the law of the Universe of Cause and Effect**: one creates the cause and an effect follows. Someone puts the seed in the ground and it will sprout. If there is the cause, the tree is the consequence. Somebody causes harm, he gets a demand to compensate this harm. One prepares the case and an effect comes from it. It is the most intimate bond that exists in all life processes, including politics, law/justice reform, decision-making, legal services.

With the words of universal wisdom, Jesus put his fingers into the man's ears: the touch of the fingers speaks without words. Jesus enters into a bodily relationship and touches the weak parts, like a doctor, he touches the suffering ones. Then, spitting on his own fingers, he touched the man's tongue. It goes done only when someone kisses other intimately.³³ How it could be different to you if while a politician or a judge/lawyer explains your rights, he also holds your hands, hugs you and kisses you! It could be different, but it is unreal. But it's true that a judge/lawyer should take care of your case, as it was true in the Soviet civil procedure, with its **Principle of Objective Truth**.³⁴ We are agree with Embulaeva Natalia and Inickaya Lyubov that it is necessary to interpret the principle of objective truth as universal one, which must permeate not only the sphere of law enforcement, but also the formation of laws. A proposal is formulated on the need to separate and normatively fix the principle of objective truth in the procedural branches of law as an independent principle (The principle of objective truth in law, Web Conferences (January 2018) ³⁵ Every injured person needs to feel "taken by the hand", welcomed, he must feel that the judge is there for his case, attentive to his case and then the judge has to exercise discretion, to do justice, because mechanical following the law is not enough! A.Koni³⁶ said

30 Carlo Rovelli is an internationally renowned theoretical physicist who during his career has worked mainly in the field of quantum gravity and was one of the founders of the theory of loop quantum gravity. Carlo Rovelli also deals with the history and philosophy of science. In *Helgoland* Rovelli delves into revolutionary theory, first allowing us to understand its theoretical and practical value, and then exploring the issues that make quantum theory one of the most mysterious physical theories science has to do with. These mysteries have been at the center of the research of physicists, philosophers and other great thinkers for years: Rovelli focuses on the relational interpretation and on the links between this interpretation and oriental history, art, literature and philosophy. The author leads to discover how this view of quantum theory can lead us to reconsider the way in which we think about reality.

31 Thích Nhất Hạnh (1926) is a Zen Buddhist monk from Vietnam, writer, poet, and human rights activist. He lives at Prem Village Monastery in the Dordogne region of Southern France, traveling internationally to give retreats and speak. Thich Nhat Hanh has published more than 100 books, including more than 40 in English. He is active in the peace movement, promotes non-violent solutions to conflict and also refrains from consuming animal products as a means of non-violence against non-human animals.

32 Green Celia, *The Lost Cause: Causation and the Mind–Body Problem*, Oxford: Oxford Forum (2003). Includes three chapters on causality at the microlevel in physics. Bunge Mario, *Causality: the place of the causal principle in modern science*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press (1959), Bohm David, *Causality and Chance in Modern Physics*. London Taylor and Francis (2005), Miguel Espinoza, *Théorie du déterminisme causal*, L'Harmattan, Paris (2006).

33 Mark, 7:33.

34 See in detail: https://www.shs-conferences.org/articles/shsconf/pdf/2018/16/shsconf_icpse2018_02011.pdf
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/20098105>
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/838196>

35 See also: Ginsburgs George, *Objective Truth and the Judicial Process in Post-Stalinist Soviet Jurisprudence*, Oxford University Press, *The American Journal of Comparative Law*, Vol. 10, No. 1/2, 53-75 (Winter - Spring, 1961)

36 Anatoly Fedorovich Koni (1844–1927) was a Russian jurist, judge, politician and writer. He was the most politically influential jurist of the late Russian Empire. He participated in a number of high-profile criminal cases, including **The Borki train disaster** occurred on October 29, 1888 (Miller Frederic P, Vandome Agnes F, McBrewster John (eds) *Borki train disaster: Kharkov Governorate, Kharkiv Oblast, Royal train, Tsar, Crimea, Saint Petersburg, Alexander III of Russia*, 2010), **the shipwreck of Vladimir** (the captain of the Russian steamship Vladimir and the captain of the Italian steamship Columbia were put on trial in this case. They were accused of committing incorrect maneuvers, admitting violations of the rules on the safety of traffic at sea, which caused a collision of steamers, the death of the steamer Vladimir, 70 of its passengers, 2 sailors and 4 people from the service personnel. The collision of steamboats occurred

that “the officials of the judicial competition must not forget that in a certain sense the court is a school for the people, which teaches not only to respect the law, but also to serve the truth and respect human dignity.”³⁷

We should know how to appreciate it, **the principle of objective truth** of the Soviet civil procedure, which accompanied someone in need to justice.

Sometimes everyone needs to feel the importance of having the just judge next to his case, because the right presence doubles his strength, increases his esteem, soothes the pain. A.Koni confirmed that in a trial “grace <...> was a higher blessing than mechanical adherence to the letter of the law..”³⁸

We refer to the second law, we need to know: **the cause follows the effect.**

For thousands of years, **the law of cause and effect** guided scientific inquiry. In fact, the history of **the concept of causality** can be traced through Hebrew, Babylonian, Greek and European cultures. Certain Greek philosophers, however, introduced the atomistic concept of chance-events to oppose the common-sense application of causality. The resulting conflict between **cause versus chance** has not only shaped the history of science but has imposed lasting effects on Western culture as a whole. This conflict intensified during the Twentieth Century as the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle (HUP) became the leading tool of the proponents of chance. More recent findings have now demonstrated that the HUP fails. Common Sense Science counters chance-based philosophy by returning to causality and other principles of Classical Science.

Creative models. This paper shows how creative models based on the laws and precedents can fully implement the law of cause and effect in manner of quantum theory. Be just and you will not do injustice, bad lawyering, unjust policies!
Be just and friendly face of justice/good lawyering/just policies will appear.
Be just and everything else follows.

It seems strange, doesn't it? With the universal wisdom Jesus Christ says the same thing in different words: “But seek first the kingdom of God and his righteousness, and all these things will be added to you..”³⁹ The Kingdom of God is the effect. He says: first seek the end, the cause will follow. This is how it should be. It is not only true that if you put a seed in the ground you will get a tree; it is also true that if there is a tree, there will be millions of seeds. It is not only true that if a judge/lawyer **choose that which is just by the law, he achieves justice.** It is also true that if there is **justice**, there are millions of **judges/lawyers' choices of that which is just by the law.** If the cause is followed by the effect, the effect is again followed by the cause. It's a chain! Then it becomes a circle. Modern physics says that it is easier to create the effect than to create the cause, because thought affects reality⁴⁰. D.Gabor stated: “You cannot predict the future, but you can create

on the night of June 27, 1894- <https://law.wikireading.ru/18245>), was the author of such works as "Fathers and Sons of Judicial Reform", "Judicial Speeches" and "On the Path of Life". Among his contemporaries, Koni became famous as an outstanding orator.

37 See: Koni A.F, Izbrannye trudi e rechi (Selected works and speeches), Yurayt (2019).

38 Ibid.

39 Matthew 6:33 ESV.

40 HERE ARE 7 INCREDIBLE DISCOVERIES THAT PROVE THE POWER OF THE MIND: STUDY #1: VISUALIZATION CREATES RESULTS: Australian Psychologist Alan Richardson set out to prove the power of visualization through an experiment. (<https://www.expertenough.com/visualization-works/>)

STUDY #2: SMILING IMPROVES MOOD: One of these studies took place in the late 1980's (<https://theeconomyofmeaning.com/2016/08/20/famous-psychology-study-killed-by-replication-does-a-pencil-in-your>

it.”⁴¹ It depends on everyone, completely, while the cause may not depend on everyone, completely.

According to quantum physics, we are all part of a reality that we create as we observe it. For this we can modify it. Paolo Scarpari, quantum physicist,⁴² explains how. His thought system opens up considerable space for human possibilities to make a change through a change of paradigm. Peter Baksa manifests that the level of our thought/brain wave is what makes our reality what it is and what it will continue to be. He reviews the quantum mechanics that supports the manifestation and the tenets of six major world religions, focusing on their teachings of prayer and meditation, and shows how these ancient truths mesh with manifestation.⁴³ Already Immanuel Kant argued that it is the mind that shapes reality. His Critique of Pure Reason illustrates the inevitable limitations of our ability to discover “reality”. Kant asserts that what we perceive to be “real” is not absolutely “real”. The brain receives stimuli from the “real” world; it organizes, processes, and shapes the stimuli in a certain fashion before feeding it back to the person. As a result, the person only perceives the already processed and shaped information. To Kant, the brain is constantly changing “reality”. His assertion is further explained as he introduces two vital terms, “phenomena” and “noumena”.

Why do we continue to view real **just policies/justice/good lawyering** as something foreign to us? Still, we could play a role in producing it. Quantum physics goes in this direction.

It started in 1909 with the experiments on the behaviour of photons carried out in a physics laboratory by Geoffrey Ingram Taylor.⁴⁴ Projected against a barrier with two holes, the particles, instead of passing through the two holes one at a time, crossed them simultaneously, which did not meet the expectations of traditional physics: they behaved as if they knew what only the scientist who conducted the experiment. The conclusion was that the observer had influenced the particle through the simple fact of being present in the experiment.

[mouth-make-you-feel-happy/](#))

STUDY #3: THOUGHT MANAGEMENT LOWERS STRESS: Don Joseph Goeway, the author of *Mystic Cool: A proven approach to transcend stress, achieve optimal brain function, and maximize your creative intelligence* has plenty of experience in this area.

STUDY #4: THE BRAIN CAN PRODUCE SEROTONIN ON ITS OWN: <https://www.healthline.com/health/how-to-increaseserotonin>

STUDY #5: PEOPLE CAN “THINK” THEIR WAY TO RELEASING WEIGHT: this experiment involved a Harvard psychologist and a group of mostly overweight hotel maids. Langer, the psychologist, predicted that the maid’s viewpoints on their physical activity made it difficult for them to lose weight.

(https://dash.harvard.edu/bitstream/handle/1/3196007/Langer_ExcercisePlaceboEffect.pdf?sequence=1)

STUDY #6: POSITIVITY AND MEDITATION PROLONGS LIFE: in 1989, Dr. David Spiegel of Stanford University took on a study consisting of 86 women in the late stages of breast cancer

(<https://www.apa.org/monitor/jun02/mindbody>>)

STUDY #7: THE PLACEBO EFFECT: pharmaceutical studies frequently employ placebos to affect the human mind and other areas as well. In fact, researchers are discovering that placebos are at times more effective than actual medication. (<https://www.health.harvard.edu/mental-health/the-power-of-the-placebo-effect>) Indeed, the power of the mind is an incredible thing.

41 See: Gabor D, *Inventing the Future*, Penguin Books (1964).

42 Paolo Scarpari is the founder of Coscienza Quantica - Institute of Evolutionary Research, researcher and scholar of the processes of determination and development of reality.

43 Baksa P, *Faith Wave I Think... Therefore It Is...*, Intelegence Publishing (2014).

44 In 1909 Geoffrey Ingram Taylor (1886-1975) set up the "Young" double-slit experiment.

In physics, **the observer effect** is the theory that the mere observation of a phenomenon inevitably changes that phenomenon.⁴⁵ This is often the result of instruments that, by necessity, alter the state of what they measure in some manner. A common example is checking the pressure in an automobile tire; this is difficult to do without letting out some of the air, thus changing the pressure. Similarly, it is not possible to see any object without light hitting the object, and causing it to reflect that light. While the effects of observation are often negligible, the object still experiences a change. This effect can be found in many domains of physics, but can usually be reduced to insignificance by using different instruments or observation techniques.

An especially unusual version of the observer effect occurs in **quantum mechanics**, as best demonstrated by the double-slit experiment. Physicists have found that even passive observation of quantum phenomena (by changing the test apparatus and passively 'ruling out' all but one possibility), can actually change the measured result.

This experiment, repeated in 1998 at the *Weizmann Institute in Israel* with more sophisticated and sensitive equipment, confirmed the result and demonstrated that the more particles were observed, the more they were influenced by the observer.⁴⁶ Despite the "observer" in this experiment being an electronic detector—possibly due to the assumption that the word "observer" implies a person—its results have led to the popular belief that a conscious mind can directly affect reality. The need for the "observer" to be conscious is not supported by scientific research. "Of course the introduction of the observer must not be misunderstood to imply that some kind of subjective features are to be brought into the description of nature. The observer has, rather, only the function of registering decisions, i.e., processes in space and time, and it does not matter whether the observer is an apparatus or a human being; but the registration, i.e., the transition from the "possible" to the "actual," is absolutely necessary here and cannot be omitted from the interpretation of quantum theory."⁴⁷

In 1935, an Austrian physicist Erwin Schrödinger published his "*Schrödinger's Cat*" thought experiment to explain **superposition** (a quantum mechanics principle stating that something exists in all possible states until it is directly observed or measured, at which point it exists only in one of its possible states). "Quantum physics thus reveals a basic oneness of the universe," - Erwin Schrödinger said. He believed that only one mind exists, and we are different manifestations of that same mind. *He didn't imply religion or superstition. This view is actually possible under the laws of physics.*

Schrödinger's philosophy is also apparent in his quote: "The world is given to me only once, not one existing and one perceived. Subject and object are only one. The barrier between them cannot be said to have broken down as a result of recent experience in the physical sciences, for this barrier does not exist." In summary, the experiment means that *reality is the result between observer and observed*. In other words, Justice/Jus Lawyering as a reality is the result between lawmaker/judge/lawyer and justice/just lawyering.

According to the interpretation developed in 1927 by Niels Bohr and Werner Heisenberg, both Nobel Laureates in Physics respectively in 1922 and 1932, known as **the Copenhagen Interpretation**⁴⁸, the universe exists as an infinite number of superimposed

45 <http://faculty.uncfsu.edu/edent/Observation.pdf>

46 Weizmann Institute of Science, Quantum Theory Demonstrated: Observation Affects Reality, Science Daily (27 February 1998), Squires, Euan J. 4. The Mystery of the Quantum World. Taylor & Francis Group (1994).

47 Heisenberg Werner, Physics and Philosophy, 137 (2007).

48 It is one of the oldest of numerous proposed interpretations of quantum mechanics, and remains one of the most

possibilities all present simultaneously as possible. The act of a person who observes those potentials determines the activation of what he is focused on: in other words, what he thinks or expects to see.⁴⁹

What prevents a complete acceptance of theories that have already been widely valued by the scientific community. They are destabilizing theories. Although this

thought has its roots in ancient oriental cultures, which considered reality as *maya* (in Sanskrit "illusion"), only a hundred years have passed since those first discoveries.

Perhaps, it will take a few generations for the change to enter the collective mind.

Ashwin Sanghi said "in quantum physics, there is a concept of entangled particles – these particles behave in the same manner even when they are apart. If this is not *maya*, what is? Scientists are still trying to find out what our universe is made of. These are the same questions our scriptures had raised much earlier."⁵⁰

Today, even quantum physics claims that reality is an illusion.⁵¹ The implications of what has been said are considerable: we are part of a reality that we create as we observe it. Starting from the work of the neurosurgeon Karl Pribram,⁵² the activity of the brain has been studied in holographic terms, i.e. the hypothesis that our brain processes reality as if it was a *hologram*: how laser light activates a static memory that takes shape, so we, who are a set of cells that emit energy, by observing and thinking activate the hologram of reality, that is, the memories present not only in our personal morphogenetic field, but also those registered in the wider electromagnetic field of which we are part.⁵³

Why then does real Politics not always correspond to how a politician would like it to be? Because the brain, through its various electric fields called "mental states", processes data and creates what a lawmaker-a judge-a lawyer perceives as reality at different speeds: Beta to mainly process the so-called external-objective plane and rational

commonly taught. See: Siddiqui, Shabnam; Singh, Chandralekha, How diverse are physics instructors' attitudes and approaches to teaching undergraduate level quantum mechanics? European Journal of Physics, 38 (3) (2017), Wimmel Hermann, Quantum Physics & Observed Reality: A Critical Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics. World Scientific, 2 (1998).

49 Dr. Michio Kaku has some interesting, sometimes similar, observations. Here is the link to his website:

<http://mkaku.org/home/?cat=59>

50 Ashwin Sanghi (born 25 January 1969) is an author of the new era of retelling Indian history or mythology in a contemporary context. (See: Khare Ghose, Archana, The retell market, The Times of India (25 December 2011). Forbes India has included him in their Celebrity 100 list. (See: Mishra, Ashish, Forbes India Celebrity 100. Forbes, 8 February 2013)

51 See, for ex: Alastair I.M. Rae, Quantum Physics, Second Edition: Illusion or Reality? Cambridge University Press (2012).

52 **The holonomic brain theory** is based on some insights that Dennis Gabor had. He was the inventor of the hologram, and he obtained the Nobel Prize for his many contributions. He was a mathematician, and what he was trying to do was develop a better way of making electron micrographs, improve the resolution of the micrographs. Holography begins to take its first steps in 1947 in a laboratory of an electrical engineering company where Gabor was working on improving the electron microscope. And so for electron microscopy he suggested that instead of making a photograph -- essentially, with electron microscopes we make photographs using electrons instead of photons. He thought maybe instead of making ordinary photographs, that what he would do is get the interference patterns. Now what is an interference pattern? When light strikes, or when electrons strike any object, they scatter. But the scatter is a funny kind of scatter. It's a very well regulated scatter. For instance, if you defocus the lens on a camera so that you don't get the image falling on the image plane and you have a blur, that blur essentially is a hologram, because all you have to do is refocus it.

53 This specific **theory of quantum consciousness** was developed by neuroscientist Karl Pribram initially in collaboration with physicist David Bohm. **Holonomic brain theory** is a branch of neuroscience investigating the idea that human consciousness is formed by quantum effects in or between brain cells. This is opposed by traditional neuroscience, which investigates the brain's behavior by looking at patterns of neurons and the surrounding chemistry.

thinking, Alpha to mainly process more inner planes, including the emotional and the lower mental, Theta to process mainly the subconscious, the part of the collective unconscious to which, consciously or not, he has joined, determining what he perceives as our sense of existing, Delta to process mainly the collective unconscious, Gamma to mainly process multidimensional reality. At the moment, Theta – Delta is supposed to process reality 500,000 / 1,000,000 times faster than Beta.⁵⁴ This means that a political actor, a lawmaker's, a judge's, a lawyer's conscious is too slow to notice it and, therefore, being unaware of it, the science calls it unconscious, in the sense that it is unknown to it. As far as a political actor - a lawmaker- a judge- a lawyer knows, the conscious represents only 10/15 percent of the processing, so it is not aware of what it is actually processing.

The politician/the judge/the lawyer creates reality as a reflection of the deep feeling he/she has of himself/herself. This means that the reality he/she observes outside him/her is a reflection of what he/she unconsciously processes at the level of the subconscious and the collective unconscious. It does not correspond to what he/she desires at the conscious level as it has a minimal impact.

If someone says that we can have justice/good lawyering only if a certain judge/lawyer follows the reform (the case), then justice/good lawyering depends on that judge/ lawyer. If someone says that we are not able to have justice/good lawyering until the certain laws appear, then justice/good lawyering depends on the legislator, on the judicial practice, on the discretion/legal creativity, on the legal and political situation and many other concrete things. It might not even happen, and then we will not see the world of justice. The cause is beyond us. The effect is within us. The cause is in the surrounding factors, in the situation - it is external. The effect is in us!

If one can create the effect, the cause will follow. If someone chooses justice/good lawyering, delicious bread, it means he chooses the effect - and then he can see what happens. His life will change immediately and he will see miracles of justice happening around him ... because he has created the effect and the causes will have to follow. It looks like magic. But it's not magic. We must simply remember that life is a causal relationship. A politician, a judge, a lawmaker, a lawyer should remember that just policies, justice/good legal services are a causal legal relationship.

In "**Helgoland**" **Carlo Rovelli**⁵⁵ confirms that quantum theory is the most radical scientific revolution of all time.⁵⁶ It turns out to be more and more full of disconcerting and disturbing ideas (phantasmatic waves of probability, distant objects that seem magically connected to each other, etc.), but at the same time capable of countless experimental confirmations, which have led to all sorts of everyday applications, of everyday application.

54 **Ned Herrmann** has developed *models of brain activity* and integrated them into teaching and management training. Before founding the Ned Herrmann Group in 1980, he headed management education at General Electric, where he developed many of his ideas. Here is his explanation:

<https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/what-is-the-function-of-t-1997-12-22/>

55 See: Bozzi Ida, «Helgoland» di Carlo Rovelli, l'isola e gli amici geniali: la fisica dei ventenni". Corriere della Sera (in Italian) (September 2, 2020).

56 Carlo Rovelli is an internationally renowned theoretical physicist who during his career has worked mainly in the field of quantum gravity and was one of the founders of the theory of loop quantum gravity. Carlo Rovelli also deals with the history and philosophy of science. In *Helgoland* Rovelli delves into revolutionary theory, first allowing us to understand its theoretical and practical value, and then exploring the issues that make quantum theory one of the most mysterious physical theories science has to do with. These mysteries have been at the center of the research of physicists, philosophers and other great thinkers for years: Rovelli focuses on the relational interpretation and on the links between this interpretation and oriental history, art, literature and philosophy. The author leads to discover how this view of quantum theory can lead us to reconsider the way in which we think about reality.

It can be said that today our understanding of **just policies, justice/good legal services** rest on this theory, which is still profoundly mysterious. The controversial **quantum theory does not not only grow in justice, in legal services** making its crucial passages evident, even for those who ignore it. But it is inserted into a new vision, where justice/good lawyering made up of the laws and juridical practice is replaced by a justice/good lawyering made up of legal relationships, of connected judge/lawyer and people, who respond to each other in an inexhaustible game of mirrors. A vision that leads us to explore, in an amazing perspective, fundamental questions still unresolved, from the setting up of law to that of judges (lawmakers)/lawyers themselves, intending they are part of law.

The law of the cause affect and the law of the affect cause are the laws of science. This is what Prof. Carlo Rovelli teaches political actors, lawmakers/judges and lawyers: to know the secrets of quantum physics.⁵⁷ Don't wait for new laws, new precedents; you have already waited long enough. Choose just policies, justice, good lawyering and you will have them. Choose good lawyering and you will have good lawyering. What's the problem? Can't you choose? Why are you unable to operate under these laws? Because your mind, the whole your mind has been educated by certain thinking. But if someone has got the damage and is seeking the reimbursement (the compensation) in court, that justice/lawyering will be artificial, it will not be a genuine justice/lawyering. But vital energy has its ways of operating. If every politician/judge/lawyer acts wholly, it becomes real just policies/justice/good lawyering. If every politician/judge/lawyer creates the effect, if he/she is total in it, he/she observes the results. Energy can make you king without a kingdom; you just have to act like a king. When all the energy goes into action, it becomes reality! Energy makes everything real. If you stay and wait for the kingdom to come to you, it will never happen. If a politician/judge/lawyer stays and waits for the justice to come to him, it will never happen. You can be an emperor; you just have to create the effect. Every politician/judge/lawyer is a decision-maker; he/she just has to create the effect. There is an old saying: laugh and the world will laugh with you; cry, and you will cry alone. If every politician/judge/lawyer can create the effect and be ecstatic, even the justice will be with every judge/lawyer, the just policies- with every politician, the trees and clouds will dance with them; then the whole existence will become justice, a celebration of it. But it depends on every politician/judge/lawyer, on whether every politician/judge/lawyer is able to create the effect. And science tells us it's possible.

Life, legal practice including, is relationships, interconnections. The thought of the Indian philosopher **Nagarjuna**,⁵⁸ who lived about 18 centuries ago, seems to provide conceptual tools to guide us with respect **to the discoveries of quantum physics and also towards judicial discretion and legal creativity.**

Nagarjuna's thought is centered on the idea that **nothing has existence in itself.** Everything exists only in dependence on something else, in relation to something else. The term used by Nagarjuna to describe this lack of self-essence is **"emptiness" (sunyata)**: things are "empty" in the sense that they have no autonomous reality, they exist thanks to, as a function of, with respect to, from the perspective of something. On the other hand Nagarjuna distinguishes two levels, as do so many philosophy and science:

⁵⁷ <https://www.illibraio.it/news/dautore/carlo-rovelli-helgoland-1388361/>

⁵⁸ Nāgārjuna (c. 150 – c. 250 CE) is widely considered one of the most important Buddhist philosophers.

conventional reality, apparent, with its illusory or perspective aspects, and ultimate reality. But it takes this distinction in a surprising direction: the ultimate reality, the essence is absence, emptiness.

Every scientist seeks an essence on which the thing can depend: the starting point can be God, spirit, Platonic forms, the subject, the elementary level of consciousness, energy, experience, precedents, laws, politics, culture or whatever. Nagarjuna suggests that there isn't ultimate substance.

There are more or less similar insights in Western philosophy ranging from Heraclitus to the contemporary metaphysics of relationships, touching upon Nietzsche, Whitehead, Heidegger, Nancy, Putnam.⁵⁹ But Nagarjuna's perspective is a radically relational one. Conventional everyday existence is not denied, it is affirmed in all its complexity, with its levels and facets. It can be studied, explored, analyzed, but it does not make sense to look for its ultimate substratum. So is the emptiness the only reality? No, Nagarjuna writes, every perspective exists only in dependence on another, it is never ultimate reality. There are different interpretations of the text, which has been commented on for centuries. Prof. Carlo Rovelli used the Nagarjuna filtered by J.L.Garfield.⁶⁰

Today the lawyers are discussing **zen, mindfulness, diligence in Law**⁶¹. And the power of ideas that today emanates from ancient lines is very interesting! How they, intersecting with our culture and our knowledge, can open us spaces for new thoughts! Because this is culture: an interminable dialogue that enriches us by continuing to feed on experiences, knowledge and above all exchanges of the various sciences, of various disciplines.

Our aim is to focus directly on ideas that influences discretion/creativity. We believe that the major transformational shifts in the world have been brought about mainly by the sciences' integration and by wisdom that doesn't know the time. We refer to integration of knowledge on a worldwide scale. The same argument applies to certain legal problems. Such is the case with *Judicial Discretion, Legal Creativity. The phenomenon of Judicial Discretion/Legal Creativity*, when is studied through a interdisciplinary lens, leads us to a number of wide-ranging considerations. Thus, court activity can be a source of almost endless wonder for scientists. This international integration of knowledge is referred to as globalization. Otherwise stated, the need of the hour is to balance national interest with international survival.

"In a single drop of ditchwater, some people can see whole crowded cities and, thus, observe large segments of life." It is one of the epigraphs of this article. It is the argument of a short tale written by H.Ch.Andersen. It shows that everything is in the eye of the beholder: the object studied, even if thought as relatively unimportant by itself, can prompt a surprising variety of far-reaching observations.

59 See: *There's Something in the Air: Life Stories from Italy and India* (Angeloni Lorenzo, Verrone Maria Elettra eds).

60 Garfield, Jay L, *The Fundamental Wisdom of the Middle Way*, Oxford: Oxford University Press (1995). Jay L. Garfield describes that Nāgārjuna approached causality from the four noble truths and dependent origination. Nāgārjuna distinguished two dependent origination views in a causal process, that which causes effects and that which causes conditions. This is predicated in the two truth doctrine, as conventional truth and ultimate truth held together, in which both are empty in existence. The distinction between effects and conditions is controversial. In Nāgārjuna's approach, cause means an event or state that has power to bring an effect. (Garfield, Jay L , *Dependent Arising and the Emptiness of Emptiness: Why Did Nāgārjuna Start with Causation?*, *Philosophy East and West*. 44 (2): 219–50 (April 1994).

61 See, *inter alia*: Shailini George, *The Cure for the Distracted Mind: Why Law Schools Should Teach Mindfulness*, 53 *Duquesne L. Rev.* 215 (2015) .

We are a first hint of what the consummation between Buddhadharma and global politics of judges/lawyers might look like--and how to get there.

This paper presents the following main aspects of our contemporary research of the future: *the future is complex, made of granules, particells and its various images are interacions. Future is interrelations which we create today. We prove the necessity of studying the future to correct the present by creating and transforming legal ideas, legal practices and value orientations through Mindfulness in Law.*

The Mindfulness is for development, unity of diversity, inclusion and sustainability.

May our perspectives and practices inspire, inform and nurture the next generation of political leaders, judges, lawyers, professionals --since we are all vital living 'cells' in the body of this one world--as we ponder and hopefully contribute in ways little and big to the health of the body-politician, the body-judge, the body-lawyer, the body-professional which is nothing less now than the health of not just the nation but the whole world.

We want to make a contribution on how to skillfully address the current state of political affairs, judicial/legal politics. We don't pretend to give all the world needs but we give our small part. "Not everything that counts can be counted, and not everything that can be counted counts"⁶²

62 The quote, often attributed to Einstein, first appears in William Bruce Cameron's 1963 text, *Informal Sociology: A Casual Introduction to Sociological Thinking*. While one of the two parts of the quote probably already existed in some different form, Cameron was the first to put the two sentences together and seems to have coined at least one of them. The first reference to Einstein dates back to 1986, more than thirty years after the scientist's death, in the business book, *Peak Performance*. In that book it was claimed that Einstein had written this quote on the whiteboard in his office at the Institute for Advanced Studies in Princeton. Moreover, in the same book the quotation was attributed to George Pickering: <https://quoteinvestigator.com/2010/05/26/everything-counts-einstein/>